

AN OVERVIEW OF THE THEORY OF MOTIVATION IN ORGANIZATIONS AND PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract

The basis of the concept of personnel management in an organization, where a person becomes a determining factor in production, is the growing role of the employee's personality, knowledge of his motivational attitudes, the ability to form and direct them in accordance with the tasks facing the organization. In this article characteristics of motivation and different factors affecting motivation of employees are reviewed to give theoretical and practical recommendations.

Keywords: Motivation, theory of motivation, human resource management, organizational behavior.

Among the most important problems of personnel management, of course, should be attributed to the issues of employee motivation, which occupy a central place in the entire management system. Motivation in this case acts as an incentive for the behavior of personnel. The orientation of employees to achieve goals, in fact, is the main task of managers and all management personnel (Soyez et al., 2009). Recently, in connection with the change in the nature and content of labor in conditions of scientific and technological progress, extensive automation of labor processes, computerization of production, the use of complex technologies, the importance of motivating organizational behavior and material incentives for employees of enterprises has significantly increased. Motivation continues to grow as the educational level of the staff increases, as well as due to the social expectations and aspirations of all employees for justice and social security of the population. In a way, all this complicates the content of management activities, but it is the performance of the functions of management personnel that should be aimed primarily at strengthening the motivation and organization of incentives for ordinary workers. For the effective operation of any organization, responsible and proactive, highly organized, and competent leaders and specialists are required, striving, on the one hand, for the labor self-realization of the individual, and on the other, showing daily concern for the welfare of labor collectives (Yuriev et al., 2018). Management employees must see and realize the meaning of their activities in this, which is supported by the desire to achieve the goals of the organization, to obtain high labor results, to increase the efficiency of production and distribution. In economics, there are many definitions of motivation as the most important factor influencing organizational behavior.

A number of scientists give the following definition of motivation and incentives: "Motivation as a strategy for overcoming the labor crisis is based on a long-term impact on the employee to change the structure of value orientations and interests of the employee according to the given parameters, the formation of an appropriate motivational core and development on this basis of labor potential. This impact, in contrast to stimulation, is called motivation.

Stimulation as a tactic for solving the problem is an orientation towards the actual structure of value orientations and interests of the employee, towards a fuller realization of the available labor potential (Maki et al., 2016).

Motivation and stimulation as management methods mutually complement each other, although they act in different directions: motivation is aimed at changing the existing situation, and stimulation is aimed at consolidating it. Their processes can coincide and mutually reinforce.

In economic science and in the practice of the leading countries of the world, there are enough different theories of motivation. They all try to explain the corresponding phenomenon (Yuriev et al., 2018).

Motivation is the process of encouraging someone (an individual or a group of people) to take action to achieve the goals of an organization. Motivation is necessary for the productive implementation of the decisions made and the planned work. Due to the dominant role of socio-economic conditions, various motivation methods can be effective even when they are based on incorrect assumptions (for example, Adam Smith's concept of "economic man"). Modern theories of motivation are based on the results of psychological research (Maki et al., 2016).

Needs are the conscious absence of something that causes the urge to act. Primary needs are genetically inherent, while secondary needs are developed during cognition and gaining life experience. Needs can be met by rewards. Reward is what a person considers valuable to himself. Managers use external rewards (cash payments, promotions) and internal rewards (a sense of success in achieving a goal) through the work itself. The needs of the higher levels do not motivate a person until the needs of the lower level are at least partially satisfied. However, this hierarchical structure is not rigid and strict. International managers should keep in mind that the relative importance of different needs of people can vary from country to country, especially if they are at different levels of development (Wesselink, Blok & Ringersma, 2017). Within the framework of procedural theories of motivation, the motivating role of needs is also assumed, however, motivation itself is considered from the point of view of what makes a person direct effort to achieve various goals.

Typically, leading American companies perform material reward procedures that are based on a competitive, market nature. The conditions for the formation of labor markets are necessarily considered here, but the main thing is that there is a direct link between the labor contribution of workers with payment and promotion. For this, it is important to determine the functions of employees, their powers, and responsibilities, as well as to assess them because of the attestations carried out. The description of labor functions corresponds to the indicator of expert assessments, which is formed by ten factors. This indicator is complex, consisting of the sum of expert assessments. Each assessment depends on the degree of involvement and the corresponding factor in the actual performance of labor functions. Engagement is characterized by numerical ratios. The ten factors include the following: knowledge, professional experience, judgment, manual labor, responsibility for the use of materials, responsibility for equipment, psychological stress, physical effort, working conditions, harm as a risk of injury (Webb et al., 2013).

The system of motivation in Kazakhstani organizations is structured somewhat differently. But at the beginning it should be noted the crisis moments in the labor activity of the personnel of various organizations. A labor crisis is clearly developing, namely, labor values have been devalued, labor has turned from the basis of a way of life into a means of survival. Labor has lost its meaningful function. The formation of a strong work motivation requires that the meaning of work is not only in the satisfaction of material needs. The purpose of labor is much broader and more significant. Attempts to create a system of motivation through denationalization and privatization have not yet yielded the expected results. The release of the labor force, the creation of competition in the labor market did not lead to stimulation of labor and to an increase in the qualifications of personnel or the development of initiative and creativity at work. As a result, there is a degradation of the labor force. Consequently, overcoming crisis phenomena in motivation is possible only because of state programs and firm state social policy. A way out of the

crisis is impossible without a regulatory role of the state in this area.

Particular attention should be paid to encouraging entrepreneurship. Since entrepreneurship is one of the important qualities of executives, in addition to its development, it is necessary to provide for its stimulation (encouragement). To form a system for encouraging entrepreneurship, it is necessary, firstly, to assess the activities of a manager not only by the results achieved, but also by the negative consequences arising from avoiding making decisions within his competence. Thus, the assessment criterion is the degree of use of the opportunities available to the manager. Thus, in general, the existing theories of motivation, which give a picture of a person-worker, with their creative use, should be the main guideline for practical activity in the field of motivation and stimulation of the work of personnel of organizations.

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